

Reliable science to inform discussions at the Heads of Delegation (HODs) meetings

Reliable science is needed to inform and support negotiations for an effective Global Plastics Treaty. In preparation for the in-person, informal HoDs meetings, members of the [Scientists' Coalition](#) have prepared this document to facilitate the proposed dialogue by ensuring delegates have access to robust, independent scientific information. The information provided follows the four Clusters of pre-determined sets of topics as outlined in the Chair's [meeting agenda](#).

This document is divided into five sections relevant to [Cluster \(A\)](#), [Cluster \(B\)](#), [Cluster \(C\)](#), [Cluster \(D\)](#), and [additional topical discussions](#) to be facilitated by the Chair. While many important topics are included in these Clusters, we note that several vital topics central to the treaty's effectiveness (e.g. scope, sustainable production) are not within the clusters for this meeting; we discuss these [elements not included at this time](#) below. **The science is clear that an effective treaty requires a full life cycle approach, as mandated by [UNEA Resolution 5/14](#), and that this scope is essential in establishing provisions that will enable the identification and equitable implementation of safe and sustainable solutions for all members.**

Cluster: (A)

Discussions will address national plans, reporting, implementation and compliance and effectiveness evaluation. The Scientists' Coalition has the following evidence-based recommendations and resources to support discussions in Cluster A.

Science-based recommendations for the consideration of member states	Scientists' Coalition resources
Access for all supply chain actors to accurate data, reporting and information exchange , particularly from upstream activities including raw material acquisition and production of virgin plastics to ensure all handling, use, manufacture, consumption, and management activities are safe, effective, efficient, and sustainable.	Supply and Sustainable Production (English , French , Spanish)
Reporting on production volumes as well as releases and leakages of pellets, powders, and flakes starting at upstream stages.	Pellets (English) Monitoring (English and French)
Monitoring of plastics pollution at upstream, midstream and downstream stages of the plastics life cycle is essential for effective implementation of treaty	Monitoring (English and French)

<p>obligations at multiple scales of governance. Accurate monitoring and reporting, compliance measures and effective implementation of national plans depend on the quality and efficacy of transparency provisions (labeling, tracking, and tracing).</p>	
<p>This Cluster currently overlooks the following important topics:</p>	
<p>Transparent reporting of chemicals used in, present in, and released from virgin and recycled plastics, entire products, and packaging.</p> <p>We emphasize that the United Nations recognizes that information on the risks and harms caused by hazardous substances should not be considered confidential.</p>	<p>Plastic chemicals (English, French)</p>
<p>Science-based definitions of specific terms.</p>	<p>Definitions (English, French, Spanish)</p>
<p>Subsidiary body(ies) that ensure assessment, monitoring, and evaluation of treaty effectiveness. Accessible guidance from independent experts for effective information exchange and public information and awareness. Evaluations of treaty effectiveness depend on the quality and availability of relevant data and reporting mechanisms.</p>	<p>Science-Policy Interface for the Plastics Treaty (English, French)</p> <p>The role of independent science in helping negotiators find common ground</p>

Cluster: (B)

Discussions will address releases and leakage, existing and legacy plastic pollution, plastic waste management, plastic products design and plastics products. The Scientists' Coalition has the following evidence-based recommendations and resources to support discussions in Cluster B.

Science-based recommendations for the consideration of member states	Scientists' Coalition resources
<p>Releases and leakages of plastics occur across the full life cycle, starting with the production of plastics.</p>	<p>Releases and leakages (English, French)</p> <p>Microplastics (English, French)</p>
<p>Reporting on production volumes as well as releases and leakages of pellets,</p>	<p>Pellets (English)</p> <p>Monitoring (English, French)</p>

powders, and flakes starting at upstream stages.	
Provisions for globally harmonised standards, monitoring and reporting for the safe, transparent, and sustainable removal of legacy plastic pollution and the remediation of contaminated environments.	Legacy plastics (English, French)
Equitable access to effective, safe, and sustainable waste management infrastructure (dependent on Cluster C and Just Transition, Cluster D).	Waste management (English, French, Spanish, Arabic)
Prioritising global reduction of the production and consumption of plastics facilitated by globally harmonised standards, reporting, and compliance measures for transparent and environmentally and socially responsible waste management.	Supply and Sustainable Production (English , French , Spanish)
Essentiality, safety, sustainability, and transparency assessments for alternative and substitute materials including bio-based plastics, biodegradable plastics , and alternative technologies, systems, and services.	Bio-based plastic, biodegradable plastic & bioplastic (English, French, Spanish, Arabic, German)
Globally harmonised product design standards guided by essentiality, safety, sustainability and transparency criteria to prevent plastic pollution.	Product Design (English , French)
Controls on the production of problematic and unnecessary plastic materials and products to reduce cost and environmental and health burdens at waste management phase, as well as those borne by the removal of legacy plastics, and the remediation of contaminated environments.	The essential use concept (English, French)
This Cluster currently overlooks the following important topics:	
Human Health is of central consequence and essential to include when discussing safer and more sustainable product design, including the regulation of chemicals of concern.	Policy brief Human Health in the Global Plastics Treaty (English, French) One health Sci Co statement (English, French, Spanish) Benefits of regulating chemicals of concern (English, French, Spanish)

	Plastic Chemicals (English, French)
Science-based definitions of specific terms.	Definitions (English, French, Spanish)

Cluster: (C)

Discussions will address capacity-building, technical assistance, technology transfer, including internal cooperation, and financial resources and mechanism. The Scientists' Coalition has the following evidence-based recommendations and resources to support discussions in Cluster C.

Science-based recommendations for the consideration of member states	Scientists' Coalition resources
Technical assistance will benefit from guidance by independent scientific, health, and technical experts including Indigenous knowledge holders.	Science-Policy Interface for the Plastics Treaty (English, French) The role of independent science in helping negotiators find common ground
An effective and just financial mechanism is crucial to operationalize every treaty provision, and to support implementation. Spanning the full lifecycle, financing strategies and obligations would benefit from alignment with core environmental principles and human rights, with measures that avoid burden shifting and promote accountability.	
This Cluster currently overlooks the following important topics:	
International cooperation ensuring complementarity with other MEAs while addressing the gaps	See table 1 in this policy brief: Article 7 on Releases and Leakages: Why is this article important and what could be improved?

Cluster: (D)

Discussions will address the preamble, objective, principles and approaches, just transition, health, public information, awareness, education and research. The Scientists' Coalition has the following evidence-based recommendations and resources to support discussions in Cluster D.

Science-based recommendations for the consideration of member states	Scientists' Coalition and other relevant resources
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<p>The objective (and scope) reflects Resolution 5/14 - to end plastic pollution while protecting human health and the environment through a full life cycle approach.</p> <p>Pollution occurs along the full life cycle. Obligations are required all along the supply chain and at all life cycle stages to end plastic pollution.</p>	<p>UNEP Resolution 5/14</p> <p>Fact Sheet: Plastic pollution at each life stage</p>
<p>Plastic pollution is a multi-dimensional issue. Framing plastic pollution beyond an environmental and waste management issue will help protect the most vulnerable populations and future generations from plastic pollution.</p> <p>Implementation of the treaty will require financial, capacity, and technical support to enable effective implementation of parties' obligations to the future instrument.</p>	<p>Plastics and the Triple Planetary Crisis (English and French)</p> <p>A just transition away from plastic pollution (English, French, Spanish, Arabic)</p>
<p>Promoting a just transition ensures that measures taken to end plastic pollution are fair, equitable, and inclusive for all stakeholders and rights holders across the plastics lifecycle irrespective of geographic location.</p>	<p>A just transition away from plastic pollution (English, French, Spanish, Arabic)</p>
<p>Scientific evidence of the global scale of all forms of plastic pollution and the extent of human exposure and related known and emerging health hazards constitute a severe and evolving global health concern.</p>	<p>Human health in the GPT (English, French)</p> <p>Article 19: Human Health (English, French)</p>
<p>It is necessary to consider plastic threats across the full life cycle in the One Health context.</p>	<p>One Health (English, French, Spanish)</p>

Topics to be facilitated by the Chair

Additional topics of importance include discussions on **scope**, decision-making, inclusive of: Conference of the Parties, amendments to the Convention, adoption and amendment of annexes, and arrangement of elements in text.

Further, the Chair has indicated that additional topics may benefit from later discussion. These include **definitions, subsidiary bodies**, secretariat, and final provisions (excl. Amendments to the Convention; and Adoption and amendment of annexes).

Elements not included at this time

The Scientists' Coalition supports evidence-based decision making, based on robust, independent science, free of conflicts of interest, with the goal of fulfilling the mandate of Resolution 5/14, to end plastics pollution. An effective treaty will address plastics across **the full life cycle**, and will take a **rights-based approach** to protect environmental and human rights.

Several topics that have cross-cutting relevance in the treaty and that are fundamental to the discussion of other topics identified within the Clusters, are not currently included for discussion in the Clusters. These include **Article 2 Definitions** (see [Comments on Article 2: Definitions](#)), and **Article 6 sustainable production** (see [Achieving a primary plastic production target](#), [Upstream reduction of primary plastic polymers](#), [Cutting Plastic Pollution at the Source](#)). **These topics are critical to the overall success of the treaty.** We are concerned to ensure that these topics, included in the Chair's Text of 1/12/24 and which are essential for effective delivery of the UNEA 5/14 mandate, will receive scope for full and inclusive deliberation.

Article 20bis Subsidiary Bodies (see [Science-Policy Interface for the Plastics Treaty](#)) may be considered for later discussion. However, evidence-based process will facilitate informed decision making and assist member states in finding common ground. In addition, early discussions will be needed about the types of independent expertise and evidence needed to facilitate the effective implementation of the treaty.

We note that the key topic of **Human Health** has been positioned in Cluster D along with important, but unrelated topics (Preamble, objective, principles and approaches, just transition, public information, awareness, education and research). Scientists' Coalition members stress the importance of addressing human health in the treaty, including [plastic chemicals](#), noting that this cross cutting topic could be addressed in a standalone **Article 19** (see [Comments on Article 19 on Health: Human Health in the Global Plastics Treaty](#)), and as a cross cutting topic and thus, incorporated into the preamble and objectives.

Are you a negotiator looking for scientific evidence or support related to the Plastics Treaty? Please contact us via secretariat@scientistscoalition.org to set up a confidential meeting.

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